

Sociological Trilogy of Cultural Community on Exposure Peril of Monsoon in Western Rural and Urban, Sierra Leone

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Abstract:

Although there are crowds of cultural comprehension and interpretations, the mass of Sierra Leonean sociologists would consent that the anchor of Sierra Leonean sociology is the swotting of personage reciprocation (Bangura, 2019). Consequently, when exposure pounds, Sierra Leonean sociologists have asked, “how do Sierra Leoneans reciprocate?” The natural social standard of intermittence or frequency and ferocity of hydro-meteorological exposures stirring Western Rural and Urban is socially augmenting, preeminent to tough shivers shocks on socio-economic, educational

and cultural growth (Jackson, 2023; Wouter Botzen et al, 2019). This social research pinpoints at charting the social judgements of the illustrative social history on the shock of cultural community-predicated social arteries to exposure foresight to the peril of typhoon activated monsoon in Western Rural and Urban, Sierra Leone. The judgements of this social research might bolster link social lacunae in cultural community foresight and imminent social antiphon to the peril of typhoon monsoon, consequently abridging social susceptibility and exposure. Fundamental dossier for social research was captured via online partially-structured social dialogues. Seventy-eight social research respondents were affianced for a profound sociological comprehension of the shock of cultural community predicated arteries on exposure foresight. Auxiliary dossier was collected via social evidence inquiry by scanning, appraising and reviewing briefs and inferences from previous social research discourses, monographs and peer reviewed journals. The Estimate-Talk-Estimate social technique was utilised to assess the impact of cultural community based arteries to exposure foresight. The extensive social research judgement was that cultural community-accustomed practice has a substantially lofty shock on individual threshold of exposure foresight. The social research suggested policy makers to proliferate the social accomplishment of cultural community accustomed exposure oversight practice blueprints as the maximum reasonable scheme to diminish the shocks of typhoon activated monsoons in Western Rural and Urban, Sierra Leone.

Keywords: *Sociological, Cultural Community, Exposure Peril, Monsoon, Sierra Leone.*

Introduction

From the social dawn, commencing with Turay’s and Gbetuwa’s (2022) initial research on exposure oversight in Sierra Leone, this has been the pivotal inquiry that expounded the sociological research agenda of Western Rural and Urban, Sierra Leone. The rudimentary

noetic affirmation was that although all exposure incidents were distinctive or exceptional social episodes, relative diagnoses could observe features of commonality that is extraordinary social patterns of behaviour. Sierra Leonean sociological researches have encapsulated behaviours of individuals and their social sections, stretching from households, rural

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childhood, to social associations to cultural communities and post traumatic social disorders and homelessness (Bangura 2019; Kabba 2022; Schneider 2022; Bolotta and Devine 2021; Steidl, 2022; Fullah, 2023). Further currently, under the University of Sierra Leone, Fourah Bay College, Department of Sociology and Social Work Higher Education Curriculum Development (Social Work and Disaster Management, 2021) constructed exhaustive literature synopses for lecturers of courses designed on the social dimensions of exposure. Collectively, these numerous synthesizing statements integrate the social research judgements from series of post-disaster field social researches. Although foresight and alleviation engagements have been researched, the combined cluster of such social inquires, like those investigating causation or inducement of exposure, fade in contrast to the social character of post-incident appraisals (Sawaneh et al 2023; Sesay and Bradley, 2022; Frazer, 2020; Musoke et al, 2019).

Since 2017 and in July 2023, the frequency of typhoon emanating from the Konakridde axes stirring Western Rural and Urban Sierra Leone has been augmenting, regularly directing to harsh monsoon, mudslide and other shapes of hydro-meteorological exposures. The ferocity and intermittence of climate transformation associated exposures in the Mano River Basin, Sierra Leone comprised, is calculated to augment in the eventual, ascribable to universal temperature change activated excessive meteorological incidents for instance, monsoon engagement in the Atlantic Ocean and its shock (Yila et al, 2023). Repeatedly, owed to temperature change, considerable socio-cultural localities are predicted to contact momentous divergences in rainstorm intermittence and sequences, directing demand for more advanced foresight suitable to alleviate the shocks (Liu, et al). This is also factual for Sierra Leone where the trend of tropical storm activated monsoons has persisted to augment until the present day with most recently, Typhoon Guinea-Conakry hitting Western Rural and Urban in 2017 leading to 1,141 deaths, affecting 1,256,860 sq ft, 3,000 displacements and extensive damage to infrastructure valued at about \$4 million and in

2023 leading dozens of death and loss of infrastructure valued at \$1 Million dollars.

Consequently, the demand for cultural community constructed threat palliation evaluations and shrinking susceptibility amidst cultural communities in Sierra Leone becomes a priority affair to mitigate fatalities and mislays generated by typhoon activated monsoon exposures (Zeng, 2023).

The immense repercussions and plate of monsoons in Sierra Leone can partially be ascribable to absence of exposure foresight measures and ability to efficiently contradict augmenting cultural community susceptibility (Turay and Gbetuwa, 2022). Further than frequently, insufficient funds, social strategy lacunae and a receptive as opposed to a receptive perspective to exposure reaction have been devised as some of the paramount elements directing to the gravity of exposure shocks in Western Rural and Urban Sierra Leone. Nonetheless, cultural communities existing in exposure vulnerable terrains deficit contemporary exposure peril knowledge and their reaction has frequently been very moderate and clumsy, further technical forecasts summarise that temperature change activated hydro-meteorological threats or perils are augmenting in ferocity and intermittence (Enu, 2023). This is also factual of the peril of typhoon activated monsoon in the Western Rural and Urban district. The district's proximity to the Atlantic Ocean where equatorial rainstorms are launched and its location along the West Guinea coast track offers it extremely susceptible to the peril of future monsoon. Further than frequently and in the previous, diminutive or no substantial correlating exposure assuagement evaluations have been recommended, affixed to slender government capability and other structured deficiencies. Consequently, accomplishing cultural community accustomed exposure reaction systems become one concrete rural and urban recourse (Shah, 2023).

Scores of social researches depict that cultural community accustomed perspectives have been efficient in bolstering foresight and alleviating susceptibility. This is so because in most

scenarios, distressed cultural communities are the foremost to react to exposures, and when constructive and coherent, have a greater possibility to mitigate shocks (Wardekker, 2023). Embracing cultural community-accustomed perspective has been proven efficient in furnishing cultural communities susceptible to exposures with adequate knowledge on exposure foresight, specifically activating swift reaction. In Sierra Leone, some district exigency exposure reaction crews might be stationed about 30 miles off from some outposts. Additionally, harmonized exposure oversight from foreign aid assistances and government normally arrive at exposure locations behind time, and social experiences noticed when typhoon Konakridee appeared, they were able to reach only a couple of the distressed outposts roughly four days behind time. Humanitarian Aid could not reach into distressed terrains due to inclement weather while roads were inaccessible as bridges and road banks were destroyed.

Previous to Konakridee typhoon in 2017, disclosure and prompt caution by the Sierra Leone Meteorological Agency of the possibility of the equatorial typhoon reaching the western rural and urban sections of Sierra Leone was rather appropriate. This depicts that accessible meteorology associated prediction gadget is authentic and sound. Nevertheless, because knowledge circulation is quite centrally managed, it did not reach out all cultural communities or terrains in suitable hour. Nevertheless, at threat or peril cultural communities did not take swift stand to evacuate referencing grounds that previous typhoon predictions spun out less devastating (Yang, 2023). Minimum awareness to conscientise the social public was given; consequently no evacuation or exigency reaction plans were triggered or effectively enforced. The experiences and attendant lessons learnt from the impacts of Tropical storm Konakridee motivated this social research, whose objectives are to analyse the impact of: a) community accustomed practice on exposure foresight b), adequate land utilisation on exposure foresights and c) social structural designs on exposure foresight in facing typhoon activated monsoon

in Western Rural and Urban, Sierra Leone. Improving the appropriateness of these perspectives has demonstrated to be effective in mitigating susceptibility and exposure to disasters. Nonetheless, numerous social researches assent that the threshold of cultural community exposure foresight is significantly associated to strength and exposure peril reduction (Nkombi and Wentink, 2022; Que et al, 2022; Johnston et al, 2022). Since these initiatives are developed at proletariat statuses, they are judged germane in generating appropriate responses to the peril of typhoon activated deluge in Western Rural and Urban, Sierra Leone.

Literature Review

Exposures have long been social entities of consideration by Sierra Leonean sociologists. Undoubtedly, prior to the 2000s the social research literature was dominated by sociologically accustomed historical discourses or summaries, followed by that of social historians like Ibrahim Abdullah, Ismail Rashid, Chernoh Alpha. M. Bah, Joseph Bangura and Alusine Jalloh. Sociologists have debated that exposures may exhibit the pivotal social appraisals and constructions that detail cultural communities and the societies they constitute. Social elements that inspire both reliability and transformation may thereby be authenticated. Consequently, both essence social behaviour patterns and the social elements that constrain them may be illuminated by the social research of exposure. And while cultural divergences may be associated with substantial deviations in reaction, cultural comparability have been authenticated by those comparing developed nations prominence to reactions by developing nations have authenticated the functional function of culture in model cultural deviation (Packer and Cole, 2023).

In most cases, Sierra Leonean sociologists have differentiated exposures from perils. Subsequently most, for instance, the Department of Sociology and Social Work, Social Work and Disaster Management as Module content (2023) defined these vocables as

follows. An exposure is “. . . an incident in which a cultural community experience grave related misfortunes to individuals or estates that the funds accessible within the cultural community are gravely donor driven.” (University of Sierra Leone, Fourah Bay College, Department of Sociology and Social Work, Student Handout, p. 3-7). This theorisation is conformable with these prospective or suggested by the initial social inquiry parties, for instance, Enu, 2023; Turay and Gbetuwa, 2022. In contrast, a peril is “. . . a circumstance with the implicit for damage to the cultural community or milieu” (Lahai and Lahai Jr, 2019). For sociologists, the vocable exposures referred to specific incidents like Monsoon (Mohan and Sinha, 2023) whereas perils define a social class of threats like monsoons, twisters, landslides, and with others. Consequently, they refer to the monsoon peril or the twister peril that echoes the peril, susceptibility, or exposure accosting households, cultural communities or associations.

Streaming from these analogues, most Sierra Leonean sociologists prospect exigency oversight as “. . . the procedure by which the uncertainties that prevail in probably risky circumstances can be mitigated and communal security augmented. The social objective is to restrict the evaluates of exigencies or exposures via the application of a chains of socio-cultural initiatives and methods contemplating complete social existence cycle of exposure involving foresight, reaction, rehabilitation, and reduction.” (Maldeniya, 2023).

Additionally, however, pivotal social affairs and anxieties have expedited much social discourse. Among these, dual are most cardinal, and obviously are pressing alternative social research schedule in very divergent supervisions. These affairs contemplate: 1) divergent interpretations of the vocable “exposure”, and 2) threshold of concentration on susceptibility and peril constructed paragon.

Obviously there are fundamental and very factual divergences in perspectives as to how the essence theory of “exposure” needs to be elucidated. To some, like Acikara (2023) the matter may best be pursued by a social media

engineer or other non-sociologically accustomed practitioner. So by juxtaposing multiple lexicons contemplating numerous divergences languages ranging from ‘Krio/Creole’ ‘KaThemne’ ‘Mende’, ‘Susu’(Sierra Leonean Languages), English and so forth, the dawns and complexities of the vocable “exposure” can be juxtaposed. Consequently, within the other minority Sierra Leonean languages such as ‘Sherbro’ or ‘Fula’, “the noun exposure has mystical, celestial, superhuman and spiritual connotations undercurrents...” (Cole, 2023). For others, like the ‘Limbas’ and ‘Kurankos’, “. . . the interpretation of the noun exposure comes from the interpretation of the English vocable of Greek dawn mishap, that is mishap.” (Chmutina et al, 2021). In contrast, ‘Kru’, ‘Vai’, ‘Krim’ and others connect the vocable to five such concepts as “considerable loss,” “dreadful occurrence,” “colossal calamity or mishap” or other such phrases that bear misery (Cole, 2023).

Others overly persist to surprise what the tip of the qualm is. And so, even as currently as 2020, statements like the following characterise the social review. “When a peril happens, it reveals a huge collection of peril, releasing unpredicted thresholds of shocks to small scale rural farmers” (Zhang et al, 2023). Notwithstanding the disparities of many others persist to utilise the vocables “exposure” and “peril” conversely.

Commencing with interpretations that are accident grounded, multiple have suggested disparities that contemplate pivotal logical attributes of exposures. Hollenbach (2022) suggested that some separate social researches could be bolstered if exposures were perceived as a unique sort of social problem. Quatrain interpreting elements of such incidents, among others, are: Foremost, duration of pre-warning, second, enormity of shock, third, purview of shock, and fourth duration of shock. Responding to criticisms from social constructionists (Oliver-Smith, 2022) who stress the social procedures whereby some incidents or perils are inclusively interpreted as communal bothers, while others are not, Sargiacormo et al (2022) stressed that “. . . the social core of exposure is the connection of historical situations and social interpretations of somatic

distress and social disturbance at the cultural community or higher thresholds of discourse.”

Such an outlook has led some to suggest detailed categorisations of disparity whereby “thresholds” of exposure might be interpreted with accuracy. For instance, by lodging exposure within a substructure of inclusive strain, Barton suggested that roots of peril (within and outside), social structure threshold shocked (household, cultural community, association), and other such elements could categorise inherent exposures from rampages, conflicts, insurrections and so forth. Further narrowly concentrated, Xia (2022) suggested a “continuum of collective stress” whereby social classes of incidents could be classed as accidents, exigencies, or exposures contemplative of social research local base or pillar.

Contemplating his symbolic interactionist theoretical perspective Wang (2023) has pressed pundits to retire from substructures concentrated completely on social psychology systematic elements of community plight incidents or the “social representatives” that “source” them. Preferably, further social research questions need to stretch the agenda, for instance what are the social procedures whereby certain sorts of plight conditions become “authorise” pedestals for social action? Why there are enormous reliefs strives after a monsoon and yet many avoid funding for programmes supporting victims of domestic violence, AIDS or beggars in Western Rural and Urban Sierra Leone?

The second crucial affair confronting sociologists who are researching exposures concerns to the paragons utilised. Most do not elucidate on the conceptual insights that might be directing their sphere of work although features of structuralism, symbolic interaction, functionalism, and other such substructures can be noticed. Many have constructed upon the “collective stress” substructures first outlined by Xia (2022) although the nomenclature regularly is revised. For instance, Li (2023) elaborated on his “perspective on social media overload on anxiety” Others have pursued the insights of social constructionists and shifted into social

research diary that regularly are dismissed by those rooted within a inclusive anxiety standpoint. For instance, Puddephatt (2021) carefully documented the “claims creating social engagements” of those who have “established” the optimist arbitration. This similar social insight allowed Salem et al (2022) to record the transposing “freehold” of terrorism, both relating the “culpability” and the “agencies” being utilised to defend the elimination of others.

In contrast, many (Lutfiah et al, 2023) have shifted to environmental social researches for support.

By stressing the social appeal of “environmentally cordial” exposure reduction strategies, theories of “legitimacy”, and “peril divulgence”, “assumption of peril accustoming” and others have reformulate the social research objective. Cultural community knowledge initiatives are established and assessed throughout the application procedure so as to direct exigency supervisors exploring to have cultural community based exposure reduction initiatives that will motivate growth that may better “exist with social cosmos” rather than opposed.

Community Lodged Exposure Peril Oversight

Community-lodged exposure peril oversight is really a wide theory that concentrates on all features of exposure pattern, from deterrence and reduction to consolation, reaction, and rehabilitation. Furthermore, cultural community-lodged exposure peril oversight is a blueprint that mitigates susceptibilities and enhances folk's capability to deal with perils. It aspires to: (1) mitigate susceptibilities and bolster susceptible cohorts and cultural communities' capabilities to deal with, intercept, or curtail loss and destruction to existence, estate, and the cultural community or milieu, (2) mitigate human agony, and (3) accelerate rehabilitation. It serves as a protection vocable for programming perspectives that involves social recipients in their recognition, devise, or

oversight, involving the collection of perspectives, employed within cultural community-threshold projects or as a constituent of national programmes.

The theory of Cultural Community Lodged Exposure Peril Oversight has also been quiet familiar in Liberia where the Nation's Exposure Oversight Section has made huge progress in empowering cultural communities with education on exposure peril oversight from proletariat threshold. Cultural communities in exposure vulnerable terrains enthusiastically engage in "Breath Life" which essentially taps on local knowledge to bolster exposure foresight. Cultural communities are coached on exigency exposure reaction and exposure information distribution via National Action Plan for Exposure Reduction platform as capacity constructing initiatives tailored regarding mitigating susceptibility and exposure.

Exposure Social Foresight

Exposure foresight or readiness is robustly associated to capability of a person, organisation, institution, cultural community or administration, to administer exposure comprehension and developed capacities so as to effectively respond and reduce impacts of disasters. Furthermore, foresight embraces competence to adequately control appearing perils or exposure perils in eventual. Exposure foresight is a procedure constituting of preference blueprints and engagements tailored towards reducing negative shocks of exposures. It holistically attribute to being on top of the exposure circumstance at the most suitable moment, involving taking rational engagements associated with perceiving exposure perils as privileges, and embrace competence constructing measures and learning how to anticipate, forecast and, where viable, reduce or bar exposures, mitigate exposure shock on susceptible cultural communities and, efficiently react to and deal with their outcomes at the local, national, regional, and universal thresholds.

Instilling efficient exposure foresight for susceptible cultural communities encountering

augmented perils existing prevalent in specific regions has been a significant component of exposure peril oversight. Nonetheless, exposure capacity and foresight is contemplated by the social inquiry of equal provident rather than receptive engagement for exposure peril mitigation and nevertheless, must be the foundation for exposure peril mitigation and constructing resilience both at the local, national, regional, and foreign thresholds. The central goals of exposure foresight are to minimize or bar estate destruction, loss of existence, and destruction to human and environmental natural resources, plus to protect the financial means of continuity for the susceptible inhabitants and social establishment unmasked to peril incidents. Numerous pundits assent that foresight is appreciatively connected to elements involving capacity, capability, and prior exposure social experience, among others. Requesting for the flowing engagement, committal, alliance, association and complete participation of all partners in exposure peril mitigation reduction are the pivotal traits towards administering an efficient exposure foresight scheme. Unquestionably, mitigated exposure shock is the objective of stringent financing in exposure foresight.

Mode

This social research utilises a case research perspective to comprehend individual threshold of exposure foresight in Western Rural and Urban area. In determining and evaluating the shock of community-accustomed perspectives to individual exposure foresight, this social research immersed a concerted procedure expressly the Estimate-Talk-Estimate Technique. The concerted procedure empowered social researchers to rate the level of shock as "considerably dominant, average or diminutive". This mode permits social researchers to purposively select eight experts in exposure peril oversight because their sentiments are deemed reliable and accurate. Partially-structured dialogues were utilised to obtain data from seventy-eight informants in Western Rural and Urban area via zoom meeting. Social Research

respondents were engaged in unrestricted conversations for a profound comprehension of the social problem under social research. A comprehensive social inquiry of prior associated literature sources involving social research journals, social research articles, and books were utilised to get profound approaches on Community Accustomed Perspective and exposure foresight. Social Researchers amply read, scanned and reviewed literature springs associated to cultural community foresight towards deluge, exposure perseverance, education and susceptibility to exposures, and exposure peril reduction among others. Social inquiry of published education enable social researchers to accumulate further perspectives on the soundness of cultural community-accustomed perspectives towards foresight to typhoon activated monsoon perils and how these could suit the socio-cultural perspective of Western Rural and Urban area in Sierra Leone.

Outcomes and Dialogue

The social research outcomes are discussed in dual portions, established on the essential motifs that materialised from the data inquiry procedure. Foremost, issues of discernments towards community-lodged perspectives to foresight towards typhoon Guinea-Conakry deluge perils are offered. The later portion concentrates on pointers of cultural community foresight to typhoon monsoon deluge perils in Western Rural and Urban area.

Cultural Community-accustomed Perspectives to Exposure Foresight Approaches

This social research analysed the following cultural community-lodged perspectives to exposure foresight, in specific to the context of Western Rural and Urban area in Sierra Leone, in the aftermath of the devastating shocks of Guinea- Conakry typhoon.

Cultural Community Practice in Exposure Peril and Foresight

The preponderance ninety four percent respondents suggested that there is a considerably towering shock of cultural community practice in exposure peril towards individual threshold of exposure foresight. Six percent others were of the conviction that practice must be integrated by sufficient funds and other outstanding elements towards exposure peril oversight. Respondents acquiesced that absence of exposure oversight practice oppose against ahead of time reaction, both for gradual and swift dawn exposures. The social findings are comparable to a social research conducted in 2021, Moyamba district, Southern Sierra Leone to determine the soundness of practice in mitigating the peril of exposure and cultural community susceptibility to exposures. Seventy four percent of the informants concurred that local threshold practice in exposure oversight was a very appropriate blueprint in mitigating the peril of exposure and susceptibility. The essential intent of exposure oversight practice was for cultural community institutional growth for dominant and common peril threats. The intents of the practice were to instruct and construct the competence of stakeholders to enhance their foresight, and react at all thresholds and ensure effective engagement in all chapters of exposure oversight among others. Practices were structured according to inception of exposure with conceivable impacts (ferocity) of each of the exposure incident on an extent of Dominant or Moderate or Diminutive on the foundation of previous social history, anticipation of exposure occurrence and susceptible citizenry.

Consequently, a United Nations Development Programme aptitude evaluation representation (shown below) was utilised to spot the demands of associates involving cultural communities and conduct appropriate social practice.

Figure 1. Capacity Development Process (CD)
 Source: UNDP, 2007

In another social inquiry conducted in Western Rural area, Sierra Leone in 2022, it was found out that institutional exposure oversight capacity recreates a very crucial function in reducing cultural community susceptibility to exposures as well as enhancing exposure strength and overall sustainability. The social research also found that preparing cultural communities with exposure consciousness through education and augmenting their comprehension of temperature transformation were considered pivotal towards augmenting cultural community capacity to completely prepare for an appropriate reaction to the peril of hydro-metrological activated monsoon. In circumstances where cultural communities do not own adequate and pertinent exposure social information, their threshold of susceptibility and peril exposure to exposures and their consequent t shocks was found to be considerably dominant. In Western area, Sierra Leone Office of National Security (ONS) officers had conducted training on some cultural communities (thirty nine point

nine) on temperature transformation and extreme rainstorm conditions. It was however acclaimed that despite having undergone practice, cultural communities in Western Rural and Urban area possessed exceedingly depressed education thresholds on temperature transformation activated threats. Very few respondents represented by only zero point nine were evaluated dominantly knowledgeable about temperature transformation activated extreme rainstorm incidents while forty six point three had diminutive knowledge. Seventeen point seven percent others had no knowledge of temperature transformation activated perils. The social judgements from this social inquiry question the effectiveness of the training programme in achieving its expected goals. Further research may require to be undertaken regarding the demeanor of respondents and the capability of Sierra Leone Office of National Security educators to convey education on temperature transformation and its shivers shocks. This is significant because depressed

education thresholds on temperature transformation activated exceeding rainstorm situations is intricately linked to dominant cultural community susceptibility to exposures. When no appreciable peril oversight steps are engaged as a matter of exigency, the problem would unfavourably shock on the accomplishment of unceasing growth objectives plus national economic legitimacy.

Grounded on the above social findings, it can be implied that competence constructing via practice initiatives focusing local cultural communities in exposure peril oversight is very significant and can fairly be adapted to Western area to bolster exposure foresight. The involvement of cultural communities in the scheme and observation of practice objectives are crucial elements in furthering cultural community control of the practice initiatives.

Proper Acreage Utilisation

Proper acreage utilisation scheming and ecosphere-lodged atmospheric oversight strategies have been promoted as efficient urgency social engagements for constructing exposure strength and legitimacy. Poor acreage utilisation methods augment losses from the increasing frequency of natural threats, apart from also unfavourably impacting on the ecological ecosystem and the socio-economic sphere. Deluge-grasslands and riverfronts are probable threats for exposure and susceptibility. Furthermore, those cultural communities, societies and industries stationed in seaside and aqueduct deluge grasslands are regarded most susceptible and prone to typhoons, rainstorms or windstorms and other deluge perils.

In a social inquiry conducted in Western area in the year 2021, it was exposed that the zone is very prone to monsoon-associated perils due to numerous elements involving its material or geological reservations. After typhoon Guinea-Conakry, some dwellings were found to be stationed along aqueducts and deluge grasslands, consequently putting dwellers at dominant peril and exposure given the augmenting temperature transformation activated peril of deluge. The

article also noted the practice of watercourse and shoreline planting or farming as one of the grounds why some yields were flooded off. Hence, cultural community exposure to the peril of Typhoon Guinea was partially due to the material or physical station of their homesteads. In Regent and Lumley villages, Western area, some houses were swept or completely engulfed by torrents as they were particularly in the typhoon's path. As such, these homesteads were further susceptible to deluge due to their augmented exposure. Most homestead sections, prophylactic institutions, academies, municipalities, and farmlands were at peril being to their proximity to and station beside watersheds and deluge-grasslands.

Multiple pundits also assent that being to crowdedness, inhabitable acreage is dwindling at a rapid estimate, extorting some cultural communities to stay on perilous and life threatening terrains where they abide exposed to temperature transformation activated perils. Indigent farming modes and overgrazing have been touted as some of the common cultural practices leading to soil erosion and deluge, also extorting folks to opt dwelling in terrains in which they may be further susceptible to the peril of deluge, cultivation, ridge gravel trips and mudslides among others. Some zonal town designing and local authorities also establish settlements in very perilous and susceptible to exposures owing to scarcity of inhabitable terrain. For instance, it is now normal to find household and infrastructure growth businesses in deluge grasslands and muddy terrains as part of municipal extension even though such locations might be exposed to mudslides. The unchecked slash down of shrubs for flak energy, intentional commencing grassland flaks in devising for livelihood cultivation acreage expanding and other divergent factors has left ridges without relevant shrubs cover in Western Rural and Urban Sierra Leone. Plausibly, shrubs and the inherent foliage have been discovered to mitigate soil wearing and deluge. In the same social stratum, social research stipulates that insufficient landmark oversight lead to shivers shock on biological variability. Deposition in tributaries has often led to diminishing water

tons, while sapping of lumbering enfold pilot to further shocks of national thaw such as arising climate and torridity in divergent parts of the nation. Nonetheless, acreage deterioration causes soil wearing whose web impact is augmented susceptibility and exposure to the peril of deluge and mudslides. Shoreline farming especially around watercourses has also been a crucial complication encountering numerous national institutions, and watertight approaches must be conceived in-order to curtail this problem beforehand. Twenty five percent of the respondents assented that sowing shrubs, mitigating pasturing and preservation cultivation were better applications to mitigate deluge. This depicts that appropriate acreage was reasonably evaluated, consequently respondents were of the opinion that there is minimum linkage between typhoon activated deluge and individual threshold of exposure foresight. Alternatively, they trust that despite these drives must be tackled, typhoon deluge was probable to affect cultural communities as it emanates from coastal engagement, consequently further endeavours should be grooved towards scientific established social research and the utilisation of prompt deterrent automation in peril or threat forecast. Nevertheless, it is a certitude that further social education and consciousness is required for cultural communities to comprehend the social network between the community and temperature transformation. Hence, the social lessons judgments from these and other prior researches, this research therefore, concurs that inappropriate acreage utilisation in Western Rural and Urban terrain, Sierra Leone significantly subscribe to peril exposure and susceptibility.

Substratum Blueprints

Some contemporary social structures are constructed to cope and blot up the shocks from probable threats. Structural elements involve material estates or dwellings buildings calculated to mitigate the overall shock of threats. In Los Angeles, California in the United States, for instance, contemporary engineering techniques are being embodied into constructing structures

to appropriately accomplish threat protection and strength (The New Wilshire Grand Centre) The establishment of embankments in deluge exposed cultural communities has also been very obliging in mitigating their associated shocks on folks and estate. Vague social elements are those elements in which social learning, social education and practice or concurrence is registered to mitigate the shock of exposure perils. This involves the utilisation of legitimate substructures (indemnity cover), augmenting cultural community social consciousness, cultural community steer practice and educational initiatives among others. In the same social stratum, to mitigate susceptibility to exposures, China is currently executing earthquake unsusceptible premises (For instance, The Shanghai Tower) which are essentially fortified and equipped with shock absorbers, added with fortified concrete consignments of 2.15 million cubic feet.

Attributing to incapability, most structures in the social research terrain do not meet contemporary qualities for entrancing shocks emanating from inclement typhoon activated deluges. Despite respondents assented that structural social fashions have a significant shock on individual threshold of exposure foresight, the administration of this element in the social research terrain was referenced as one obstacle. This approach is not normal among preponderance ninety percent of the folks who rely on livelihood cultivation and animal raising and consequently have restricted capability to situate contemporary engineering techniques to accomplish threat protection. Nevertheless, the region experience dominant downpour and is mountainous with sharp tilts in which tributaries and runnels are ever rushing throughout the year, consequently structures constructed on sharp tilts peril being crumbled by torrent typhoons. The terrain is popular for shrubs, mangrove and timber loggings, and cashew cultivation. This might elucidate why some structures are stained in wet terrains while others are built on sharp tilts or cliffs where they can barely resist noxious and robust winds linked with typhoons.

Isolated Threshold of Exposure Foresight

To peruse an individual's threshold of exposure foresight, it is significant to foremost recognise individual exposure strength touchstones. As previously underscored over, exposure foresight encapsulates social education and capabilities established over time, either via communal sagacity, social observation or conventional or unconventional practice by an institution, community or individual himself to establish some vocational reaction and rehabilitation when encountered with an exposure. The

comprehensive close outcome of exposure foresight is demonstrated via showing optimistic integrities, engagements or attitudes for instance, efficiently expecting, reaction to, and rehabilitating robust (construct-rear-stronger) aftershocks of possible exposure perils. Individual exposure foresight can be narrated as a merger of exposure learning and expertise, exposure exigency scheme, wealthy of exposure social observation and, worthy and dependable exposure information crucial for the establishment of reaction and reduction resolutions.

Table 1. Yardsticks for Exploring an Individual's Threshold of Exposure Foresight

Engagement Grasp	Accomplished	Completely Developed
Diminutive Developed or Unready	Conscious	Consciousness and Behaviour

Persons devoted towards exposure disaster foresight ardently engage and are considerably included in exposure peril mitigation procedures involving in the application and establishment of practice and premature admonition knowledge distribution. Those completely developed are very conscious of and exhibit beneficial social behaviours towards exposure peril oversight. It therefore ensues that diminutive developed persons take diminutive or no respond and do not exhibit beneficial social behaviours towards exposure reaction and in most cases are worst contrived by exposures.

Exposure Comprehension

The social education of cultural communities existing in terrains at peril for an imminent exposure is the foremost point of interest of for exposure oversight experts, if their threshold of exposure foresight is to be enhanced. Inappropriate foresight augments cultural community susceptibility to exposures. For cultural communities to have a comprehension and consciousness of exposures, prior social education of imminent or subsequent perils normal in their setting is critical. This exposure prior social education can be measured utilising

some of the ensuing touchstones among others: social education of exposure premature admonition structures, accessible evacuation choices such as dominant threshold refuges, evacuation delineates and paths, potential to carry out exposure exigency reaction, exposure social observation, and exposure mock or coaching practices.

In a social research conducted in Western area, sixty eight percent of the respondents established that they experienced premature admonition information about typhoon Guinea-Conakry and that it would make windfall into Sierra Leone. Of those, the mass eighty five percent circulate the information to other inhabitants within their cultural communities. Amazingly, nonetheless, only a few of those schooled (represented by thirty six point seven percent) took prior engagement by evacuating premature. About twelve point six percent of the respondents agreed transferring to secure locations in expectation of typhoon Guinea Conakry. Owing to factors such as absence of social education, grasp and absence of exposure social observation, a considerable number fifty two point six percent remained indoors while a few two point one percent resolved to surveillance the development of the typhoon by

observing to incoming newsbreaks on state radio and television mediums on the finest protection procedures. Some even distrust the accuracy of premature admonition knowledge presented by authorities, debating that just like prior admonitions, typhoon Guinea Conakry might not reach certain terrains. The mass of folks thought the deluges would just come to pass without notable shocks, an attestation that grasp and exposure naivety were at play leading to passivity for premature disclosure reaction. Intrinsically, this social research concurs that strengthening exposure social education among cultural communities via practice is a very significant theory for exposure peril mitigation and elevating strength, further specifically because it bolsters exposure foresight.

Exposure Exigency Scheme

Dominating about an imminent exposure or peril, without an exhausted scheme of engagement may not direct to a reduction in the overall aftermath shocks of exposures. Cultural communities demand to be influenced to fraternised, collaborate and co-habit in the establishment of a dense exigency foresight and reaction scheme. Cohort reaction and the capability to swiftly activate the scheme at the suitable moment of an exigency situation cannot be exaggerated. The threshold to which susceptible folks comprehend threats and perils they might encounter and the relevance of foresight is crucial in rescuing them during and after exposures. Furthermore, readiness and passion threats to effectively ready for imminent exposures by taking practical engagements is imperative. It ensues consequently that, establishing an exigency scheme or social strategy and conscientiously lodging the scheme into social practice via earmarked exposure foresight mock or social practice try-outs becomes a prime concern. This also further necessitates inspiring nationals to protect assets by taking indemnity asset and life cover, evacuation routes and exposure lines among others.

Social Particulars and Transmission

Through an exigency circumstance, approach to accurate and reliable social particulars is pivotal. Ordinarily, exposure victims always require understanding the current social particulars concerning the security of their household members and how they can get assist. When victims are short of dependable and functional exposure social particulars, consternation and gloom crawls in. This depicts that absence of knowledge or an obstruct to channel it generates a boundary that enhances susceptibility.

Conclusion

The shivers shock consequence effects of temperature transformation activated extreme weather incidents are estimated to persist influencing cultural societies in numerous pessimistic paths. Universally, the recurrence of rainstorms and typhoon directing to grave deluge persist to be felt further than previous, impacting one nation or zone and the other. In this esteem, executing cultural community-lodged insights towards exposure foresight has been found to be very appropriate in mitigating susceptibility and exposure. The social research concluded that cultural community-accustomed practice was considerably associated to person threshold of exposure foresight. Promptness to exposure general mitigates its consequence shocks, specifically protecting lives and destruction to critical social infrastructure. Consequently, establishing local exposure foresight perspectives become a pivotal theory in entrusting cultural communities, who in the dominant instances are the foremost to experience shocks of exposures. Structural blueprints were classified shallow in terms of shock to exposure foresight in Western Rural and Urban area, while adequate acreage utilization require to be regarded as a pivotal prime concern after practice in exposure. Taking a cue from the social observations of the 2017 of Typhoon Konakridee and its socio-economic shock on Sierra Leone, policy makers require to contemplate bolstering cultural community accustomed practice in order to augment person foresight for appearing and unpredictable peril of

typhoon deluge encountering cultural communities in Western area. It is also predominant that rural cultivation extension employees augment cultural community engagement in acreage preservation social practices as these are intertwined to temperature transformation whose shocks involve typhoon deluge and grave destructions among others. Plausibly, social practice conveyed upon persons, the essential social education and behaviours crucial for swift reaction to exposures, and this inceptive engagement taken prior an exposure pounds is robustly associated to exposure shocks. Persons prone to effective practice in exposure exigency reaction have been depicted to be accomplished and completely ready to encounter exposures. Eventually, bottom exposure consequences shocks assist construct strengthen reinforce cultural communities.

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